

C2G Summative Evaluation Executive Summary

C2G Program Evaluation Overview

The Community Collaboration Grant (C2G) program was part of the larger Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) program which aimed to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, had access to COVID-19 testing. The ultimate goal of increased access to COVID-19-testing was to reduce associated morbidity and mortality. The C2G program sought to achieve the goals of the larger RADx-UP program through¹:

- Removing barriers to COVID-19 testing in underserved communities through communication, outreach, and training
- Improving COVID-19 testing uptake, COVID-19 diagnosis, and test reporting
- Providing training and education for community members around COVID-19 testing topics of interest
- Generating culturally appropriate communication materials related to COVID-19 testing.

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supported C2G-funded projects as they served their communities. The CDCC served as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The CDCC was led by teams at two institutions, Duke University and the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, and co-led by Community-Campus Partnerships for Health (CCPH), a nonprofit membership organization. The CDCC partnered with a third-party Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team within UNC-Chapel Hill, Abacus Evaluation, to track and evaluate the RADx-UP initiative.

This final executive report describes key evaluation findings from the RADx-UP C2G program. Specifically, it presents summative findings across the five evaluation objectives (EO).

C2G Evaluation Components, Methods and Analysis

The evaluation employed the core components of the Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model² to assess the translation of innovations related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit C2G underserved communities at large. The T&E team employed the Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework^{3,4} to address individual- and organization-level effectiveness of C2G programs. Specifically, the RE-AIM framework guided evaluation of the reach, sustainable adoption, implementation processes, and long-term effects of the C2G program. The RADx-UP T&E team used a mixed-methods approach to collect and analyze quantitative and qualitative data in order to assess the five evaluation objectives (EO):

	C2G Program Records	6- and 12-month surveys	18-month interviews
EO1 – Assess the funding success of the grant application and utilization process			
EO2 – Assess testing access and uptake			
EO3 – Assess testing capacity, training, support, and community experience			
EO4 – Assess education, communication, dissemination, and capacity building			
EO5 – Assess satisfaction with CDCC administration and support			

The data presented were collected between January 2022, or the start of evaluation activities, through December 2024. Data collection activities included a review of administrative records from program governing bodies and project surveys conducted throughout and beyond the project lifecycle. Interviews collected qualitative measures and surveys collected both quantitative and qualitative measures that were used to gauge program outcomes and impacts within domains of the Translational Science Benefit Model.

Key Findings

EO1: How successful was the grant application and utilization process?

There were **70 C2G projects funded across seven funding cycles**. The table below shows the number of applications received and awarded during each funding cycle. The number of applicants per cycle varied, with the highest funding rates in the first four cycles.

C2G Project Cycle	Application Period	Number of Applicants per cycle	Number of Projects Awarded per cycle	Average Number of Days between Award Notification and Project Initiation	Application Funding Rate
Cycle 1	3/3/21 – 5/28/21	31	12	116 days	38.7%
Cycle 2	5/7/21 -8/18/21	11	6	93 days	54.5%
Cycle 3	7/2/21 -9/30/21	13	5	138 days	38.5%
Cycle 4	10/29/21 – 2/7/22	32	16	122 days	50%
Cycle 5	4/1/22 – 7/13/22	43	10	130 days	23.2%
Cycle 6	8/5/22-11/22/22	27	6	106 days	22.2%
Cycle 7	3/17/23 - 6/26/23	52	15	89 days	28.8%

EO2: How did the C2G pilot program affect testing and uptake?

Of the 70 C2G projects which reported data in the 6- or -12-month surveys — **(79.0%) were engaging their community in testing**. Additionally, an **estimated 168,000 people have been reached through C2G project testing efforts**.

Across the C2G program, the **six** most frequently reached states were **New York, California, Louisiana, Mississippi, Alabama, and Texas**. Most organizations funded by the C2G program were classified as **community center/case management, medical care, and public health**. Organizations primarily served the following underserved populations: **low socio-economic status populations, Latino populations, and Black populations**. They also primarily served vulnerable populations including **individuals with comorbidities, immigrant communities, and children**. Projects also partnered with **80 community center/case management partners and 38 faith-based organizations**.

EO3: How did the C2G pilot program affect testing capacity, training, support, and community experience?

Increasing access and uptake to COVID-19 testing was one of the most frequently identified significant changes across surveys (**30/70**). Increasing testing access and uptake was often accomplished through providing testing at table events, partnering with community organizations, and offering at-home COVID-19

tests to impact COVID-19 testing and uptake. One project described a lasting impact of testing in their community as follows:

*"The most significant change we saw was the **decrease in COVID-19 cases in Willacy County**. We hypothesized that by giving our community members access to testing kits, we would see a decrease in COVID-19 cases. Our hypothesis was correct. According to DSHS, a year ago we were averaging about 8 new cases per week that were reported. We are pleased to say that we are now averaging 2 cases per week for the last month that were reported."* (Project ID_219, Survey Data)

Across all seven cycles, generating resources to advance COVID-19 testing, and training and education were the most common project activities. Sustainability interviews conducted six months after closeout (18-month interviews) provided additional context on these activities, and responses revealed that resources entailed encouraging testing via face-to-face recruitment strategies and engaging trusted community members and organizations to facilitate testing.

EO4: How did the C2G pilot program affect education, communication, dissemination, and capacity building?

Evaluation surveys indicated that **58 out of 69 projects (84.0%)** reported providing training or education to their community around COVID-19 testing projects. Some examples of training included outreach to community members, homeless shelters, community health workers, and community leaders via educational sessions, town halls. C2G projects also highlighted the importance of clearly communicating testing availability to communities as this project described:

*"We found that **consistent communication about our [testing] schedule was key**. So we posted weekly on our social media platforms a very routine schedule. We had our hours, our location. And then as testing recommendations changed, or any sort of update related to testing was going on, we could include that there as well weekly"* (Project 28_Interview Data).

56 out of 69 (81.0%) projects reported that they developed and disseminated COVID-19 testing communication materials. Examples include handouts and culturally/linguistically appropriate materials distributed around the community, at outreach events, posted on social media, and shared at testing events. Projects also identified community outreach and engagement as a significant change across interviews and surveys. Significant community changes included building relationships with community partners and becoming a trusted messenger within their communities as significant changes related to community experience.

EO 5: How satisfied were C2G pilot projects with CDCC administration and support?

Overall, **99.0% (n=68/69)** of projects reported that they were satisfied with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support. Further, **89.0%** of projects were satisfied with the **C2G administration team's communication (n=61/69)** while **94.0%** were satisfied with the **use of communication channels (n=65/69)** and **92.0%** with **adaptations to meet needs (n=63/69)**. While projects reported high levels of satisfaction with CDCC, they also reported ways to improve CDCC support and resources in interviews, such as **simplifying the application**

process, increasing flexibility in some of the grant requirements, supporting collaboration among projects, and making localized and/or more culturally relevant information available. The resource and support infrastructure which the CDCC developed in addition to project suggestions for improvements may serve funders and research consortia aiming to provide technical assistance to multiple program grantees.

Conclusions and Implications

- The RADx-UP C2G program funded 70 projects across 7 funding cycles which were able to successfully carry out their project work in communities.
- The program through its projects advanced COVID-19 testing research by improving access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing in communities of underserved and vulnerable populations across the United States. An estimated 168,000 people were reached through C2G project testing efforts.
- C2G projects developed COVID-19 training, education, and communication materials. There was an emphasis on the need for culturally appropriate materials, one-on-one recruitment strategies, and engagement of community members in implementation strategies.
- Owing to C2G projects' short award term (i.e. 12 months), the engagement of the community was pivotal to successful implementation. Qualitative findings showed that authentic community engagement helped build and sustain relationships important for coordinating activities, sharing information, and increasing access to resources and services.⁵
- Overall, C2G projects reported satisfaction with the resources and support provided to them by the CDCC infrastructure throughout their funding period, indicating a successful model for technical assistance to multiple awardees.

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1. Community Collaboration Grant Program - RADx-UP. Accessed February 1st, 2024. <https://radx-up.org/grants/community-collaboration/>
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 3. Glasgow RE, Vogt TM, Boles SM. Evaluating the public health impact of health promotion interventions: the RE-AIM framework. *American journal of public health.* 1999 Sep;89(9):1322-7.
 4. Kwan BM, McGinnes HL, Ory MG, Estabrooks PA, Waxmonsky JA, Glasgow RE. RE-AIM in the real world: use of the RE-AIM framework for program planning and evaluation in clinical and community settings. *Frontiers in public health.* 2019 Nov 22;7:345.
 5. Taheri, C., Maras, S., Roberts, R., Yusuf, B., Carr, T., Osinuga, A., Hollars, J., Watkins, K., Raines, S., Frerichs, L., & Perreira, K. (2024). *Most Significant Change: A Technique to Evaluate Successes in RADx-UP C2G Pilot Projects.* <https://doi.org/10.17615/3jgj-g666>